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Teaching Listening and Speaking through Movie 'War for the Planet of the Apes': An Experiment

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Abstract:

Purpose of this research papers is to find out the effectiveness of the movie 'Planet of Apps' to teach listening and speaking skills. The researcher included 20 students in the control group and another 20 students in the Experimental group. The researcher took pre-test of students of both groups. He taught listening and speaking skills by using movie clips of the movie. Post-test was taken of all students to change. Post-test of Experimental group shows the development of listening and speaking skills compared to the control group.

Keywords: Edutainment, Entertainment, Movie clip, Experimental group, controlled group

INTRODUCTION

Teaching listening and speaking skills have been difficult for English teachers. Teachers are looking for new ways to teach listening and speaking skills. Teachers face while teaching. Students do not pay attention to the English subject. The movie can be a better source to teach English. Students do not like when they are taught by traditional methodology. Students like when they get entertainment while learning. If teachers take help of an element of fun and entertainment, teaching can be very interesting and easy. Students do not get bored when they are taught through movies.

HYPOTHIES OF RESEARCH

- Teaching listening and speaking skills through the movie can be an effective way to teach English compared to the traditional way of teaching
- Students can learn well through active learning Methodology.
- Students can improve pronunciation through movies.
- Teaching English through movies can kill the boredom of the classroom.

OBJECTIVE OF RESEACH.

- To see the efficiency of teaching English through movies.
- To observe the development of listening and speaking skills of students
- To check the effectiveness of teaching English through movies on pronunciation.
- To contribute to the field of ELT
- To suggest useful teaching approaches for teachers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Researcher in this study has selected 40 students of B.com for Experiment. Students were divided into an experimental group and controlled group. 20 students were included in the experimental group and another 20 students were included in the control group. Pre-test of Both groups control group and experimental group was taken. Students of the control group were taught by the researcher through the traditional method of teaching students of the experimental group were taught by the researcher through the English movie 'War for the planet of apps.' In the end, the

Result of Pre-test and Post-test is compared. Control group and experimental group are compared. The researcher has not selected a random assignment so he has selected quasi-experimental design.

EXPERIMENT

The researcher created the following worksheet to impart listening skill to students. When students did not understand properly the researcher plate movie clip twice.

(A) Choose correct option

(1) What is the mood between the man and the ape in this clip?

- A. friendly and happy
- B. tense and unfriendly
- C. confused and sad
- D. bored and uninterested

(2) What does the man notice about the ape's eyes?

- A. They are typical of an ape's eyes.
- B. They show a lot of anger.
- C. They are inflamed and infected.
- D. They seem to be almost human.

(3) What was the ape told about the man?

- A. The man is going to stop fighting in the war.
- B. The man is going to be joined by soldiers from the North.
- C. The man is going to start a war with another country.

(4) According to Caesar, why are soldiers joining the Colonel?

- A. to kill the remaining the apes
- B. to kill the Colonel
- C. to receive more training
- D. to help the apes escape

(5) Who told the ape that soldiers were coming?

- A. The ape does not say who told him.
- B. The ape's friends told him.
- C. The man's friends told him.
- D. The ape heard it from a soldier.

(6) From where does Caesar think more soldiers will come?

- A. the South
- B. the East
- C. the West
- D. the North

Speaking skills

Students are supposed to see trailer of this movie and imagine story of movie.

Students are asked to speak in themes and character of the movie.

DATA ANALYSIS

Control group shows development around 1% in posttest where Post-test of Experimental group shows development around 10%. Development is seen much in listening and speaking skills...

FINDING OF RESEARCH

Present study finds that movie ‘war for the planet of Apps’ is effective to teach listening and speaking skills of students. Students can improve pronunciation. Vocabulary also can be built. Students take active participant when they are taught through movies. Students find learning interesting.

CONCLUSION

Students are smart. Teachers have to be smarter to teach them, movies can be better source to teach them. Present study inspire future research to investigate other English movie to experiment. Future research can select some other students to make experiment. Present study contributes in the field of ELT. Teachers can get benefit of this finding to update their teaching style.

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WEB

One thing that all English teachers find familiar in teaching English is that students do not have an interest in attending English class. There is a strong requirement of doing something new to them. Students have been bored with the traditional classes of English. Even the Teacher also get bored when students do not learn well or when they have no interest. Most of the students ignore learning English because Teacher might not be teaching well with Entertainment. Students are looking for fun in this class. “Fun for Brains is fun for all (Okan 256)

If Teachers do not teach with Entertainment then students create Entertainment by commenting on teachers or unnecessary creating noise and comment. Anyhow they are looking for Entertainment. This idea compels teachers ponder on this issue. This issue is solved by edutainment. Edutainment means teaching something with Entertainment. Edutainment presents a blend of two streams: education and Entertainment merging into one. (Zorica 4090). It provides education with Entertainment. “Edutainment is a derived word that states a mixture of entertainment and education or marriage of education with entertainment” (qtd in Aksakal 1232) Edutainment presents a blend of two streams: education and entertainment merging into one. There are several research directions but the majority can be classified into two directions:

1. Educational usage of elements of entertainment; and
2. Integration of educational element into the entertainment.

<https://speechyard.com/>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ThXG-Kq-RkQ>

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